

A BRIEF REVIEW OF LITERATURE OF PRATISHYAYA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DIFFERENT SHALAKYATANTRA

Dr. Minakshi Dinkarrao Mendhe*¹, Ankush Dattatraya Khedkar²

*¹Professor in the Department of Shalakyatantra at Vijayshree Ayurved Medical Collage and Hospital, Jabalpur.

²Associate Professor and Phd Scholar in the Department of Rachana Sharir at Pmt's Ayurved College, Shevgaon.

Article Received on 05 Dec. 2025,

Article Revised on 25 Dec. 2025,

Article Published on 05 Jan. 2026

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Minakshi Dinkarrao Mendhe

Professor in the Department of Shalakyatantra at Vijayshree Ayurved Medical Collage and Hospital, Jabalpur.

How to cite this Article: Dr. Minakshi Dinkarrao Mendhe*¹, Ankush Dattatraya Khedkar² (2026). A BRIEF REVIEW OF LITERATURE OF PRATISHYAYA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DIFFERENT SHALAKYATANTRA. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(1), 823-830.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

INTRODUCTION

According to Acharya Charaka causes and occurrence of sinus and nose diseases are Restraining the Urges (Sandharana), Indigestion (Ajirna), Consumption of Dust (Rajo), To much Talking (Atibhashya), To much Getting Angry (Krodha), Odd Season (Rituvashmya), Pain in the Head (Shirobhitapa), To much Staying Awake in the Night (Prajagarati), To much Sleeping during Day Time (Swapna), Drinking Cold Water (Ambusheetai), Dew (Avashyaya), Excessive Intercourse (Maithuna), Excessive Crying (Vashpa), Excessive Smoking (Dhumai) etc. when phlegm and other toxins get collected in the head than due to above mentioned reasons the air in the head region increases and gives rise to disease of nose and cortex.

Pratishyaya is the most important diseases in the Nasarogas, and if not treated in time or with proper medications it becomes the causative factor of all the other nasa rogas.

Vatam prati abhimukham – it means the vitiated vata dosha moves in its opposite direction. Vata dosha is the dominant vitiated dosha in Pratishyaya and it vitiates the other doshas. The active types of vata doshas present in the nose are the prana and udana vayus. The direction of the prana vayu is from outside to inside. Hence when the vata dosha gets vitiated it moves in the opposite direction. Similarly, the direction of the udana vayu is from inside to outside,

and vitiation of the udana vayu will also change its direction. This retrospectively means that when the vata is vitiated, it moves in the opposite direction. The secretions or the mucociliary action takes the opposite direction and leads to the pathological changes. —Shyayo gamanam kaphadinam, tatra sa pratishyayahḥ – which means that the vitiated vata further vitiates the other doshas and takes them in the opposite direction. Hence there is an excessive secretion from the nose in Pratishyaya. —Prati kshanam shyayate iti pratishyayahḥ. Hence it can be concluded that Pratishyaya is-

A condition where there is continuous discharge, A condition where the dominating vitiated dosha is Vata, A condition where there is accumulation of doshas which further get vitiated. The secretions which are supposed to be drained through the nasopharynx are thrown out through the opposite direction i.e., through the nose.

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

ETYMOLOGY

The word pratishyaya is evolved from the “shyai” dhatu, which means to move, and when prefixed by Prati, the word —pratishyaya is formed – Paninisutra 3/1/141.

Pratishyaya means, the condition in which there is a continuous flow of secretions.

IMPORTANCE OF PRATISHYAYA

- Acharya Sushruta has devoted a separated chapter on Pratishyaya, which shows its importance.
- Acharya Charaka mentions that if Pratishyaya is not treated properly, it becomes the hetu of most of the Shirorogas.
- While describing the samanya hetus of nasarogas, Yoga Ratnakara has described the hetus of Vataja Pratishyaya as the hetu of all the Nazarogas. This retrospectively proves that Pratishyaya is the causative factor of all the nasa rogas. If Pratishyaya is treated properly at the proper time, the other nasa rogas are treated simultaneously.
- Besides a separate disease, Pratishyaya also behaves as the hetu of Hikka, shwasa, kasa, poorva roopa of Rajyakshma, upadrava of kaphaja prameha, etc.
- While describing Rajyakshma, Acharya Charaka has explained an independent samprapti of Pratishyaya, which is one of the main symptoms of Rajyakshma.
- If Pratishyaya is not treated rightly it will lead to kasa, and further to Kshyaya. According to modern science it means that if Rhinitis is not treated at the right time, it may lead to

upper respiratory tract infection (URTI) and later on lower respiratory tract infection (LRTI), which are more difficult to treat and land up in irreversible changes.

- Pratishtyaya is the only nasa roga where upadravas are explained in the poorvaroopas. It means that before the disease symptoms are seen, the complications are already present. This makes the disease difficult to treat.
- Pratishtyaya is a vatapradhana tridoshaja vyadhi and hence has to be treated very systematically.

Pratishtyaya as lakshana

- **Jwara** – Pratishtyaya is mentioned as a lakshana of Kaphaja jwara, Vatashleshmaja jwara.
- **Yakshma** – Acharya Charaka has cited Pratishtyaya as a Lakshana of Kshayajanya Yakshma, Sandharanjanya Yakshma, Kshayajanya Yakshma and Vishamabhojanajanya Shosha.
- **Gulma** – In Charaka Samhita, Pratishtyaya is mentioned as one of the symptoms of Kaphaja Gulma⁸ and Asadhya Gulma.
- **Arsha** – Pratishtyaya is mentioned as one of the symptoms of Vataja Arsha, Kaphaja Arsha in Charaka Samhita.
- **Krimi** – Acharya Sushruta has cited Pratishtyaya as one of the symptom of Kaphaja krimi.
- **Udavarta** – Pratishtyaya is one of the symptoms of Udavarta caused by Avarodha of Apana vayu, Apathya bhojana like ruksha, katu, tikta ahara, etc and Ashruvega dharana.
- **Anaha** – Pratishtyaya is also one of the symptoms of Amaja anaha.
- **Dushta Pranavayu** – Dushta pranavayu causes diseases like Hikka, Shwasa, etc. Acharya Dalhana included Pratishtyaya, Swarabheda also by considering etc.
- **Vegadharana** – Pratishtyaya is also included in the symptoms of Purishavegadharana and Ashruvegadharana.
- **Avrutta vata** – Pratishtyaya also belongs into the symptoms of Udana avrutta Pranavayu.
- **Niruha basti ayoga** – Pratishtyaya is said to be one of the Ayogya Lakshana of Niruha basti in Charaka Samhita and Basti vyapada in Ashtanga Sangraha.
- **Vamana ayoga** – In Ashtanga Sangraha, Pratishtyaya is cited as one of the symptoms of Vamana Ayoga.
- **Nasagata raktapitta** – Pratishtyaya is one of the symptoms which occur when bleeding of Dushta Rakta is stopped in Nasagata Raktapitta.

Pratishyaya as poorvaroopo

- **Rjayakshma** – Acharya Charaka has cited Pratishyaya as a poorvaroopo of Rajyakshma.

Pratishyaya as Nidana

- **Hikka, Shwasa** – Pratishyaya is mentioned as one of the cause of Hikka, Shwasa.
- **Karnaroga** – Pratishyaya is one of the prime causes of Karnarogas.
- **Kasa, Jwara** – Pratishyaya is said to be the nidana (nidanarthakara roga) of Kasa and Jwara.

Pratishyaya as upadrava

- **Prameha** – Pratishyaya is mentioned as one of the complications of Kaphaja Prameha.

Specific information

- Symptoms of Apeenasa are told the same as pratishyaya.
- Worsening condition of Pratishyaya is mentioned as the poorvaroopiya arishta of Yakshma.
- Vrana, which is formed due to krimi in Pratishyaya is Yapya (difficult to treat).
- The treatment of Badhirya and Vatatja karnashoola is the same as Pratishyaya.

Pratishyaya as yogya (indication) or ayogya (contraindication) for certain procedures

- Pratishyaya is mentioned among the diseases where Basti (Niruha Basti), Swedana, Vamana are specially indicated.
- Navapratishyaya is contraindicated for Nasya/Shirovirechana.
- Dushta pratishyaya is contraindicated in Pratimarsha nasya.
- Anuvasana basti is contraindicated in Pratishyaya.

Specific nidana of Pratishyaya

- Vitiated atmospheric vayu (polluted air) due to visha or gandha of vishakta pushpa causes many diseases, Pratishyaya is one of them.
- Intake of vikruta jala (impure or contaminated water) without shodhana (purification) causes many diseases, Pratishyaya is one of them.
- Sushkamansa causes Pratishyaya.
- Divaswapa causes vitiation of tridosha which leads to occurrence of many diseases like Pratishyaya.

- Divaswapa causes Kaphajanya vyadhi like Pratishyaya.
- If instructions like speaking, sneezing, laughing, movement, etc are not followed by the patient during the Nasya procedure, then Pratishyaya can occur as a complication.
- Vishakta vayu or dhooma (toxic air or smoke) causes pratishyaya in birds.
- If a small amount of poison remains in the body, it causes Pratishaya.
- Guru ksheera (milk which is hard to digest) causes Pratishyaya, especially in children.

Beneficial in Pratishyaya

Madira (sura, manda), Yava, Yavaka and Vatya; Shweta Sura, Gomansa, Mulaka Yusha; Rasala.

DISCUSSION

Various Acharyas have described Pratishyaya in various forms

- Acharya Sushruta has devoted a separate chapter on Pratishyaya. He has explained in details about the nidana, lakshanas and treatment also.
- A detailed description of Pratishyaya is given in the Charak Samhita, Ashtanga Sangraha, Ashtang Hridaya, Bhava Prakash, Yogaratnakara and Gadanigraha.
- In Madhava Nidana, a detailed description of the poorvarupas, lakshanas is given. Treatment of Pratishyaya is not mentioned in this classic.
- Acharya Sharadghar, in his Sharangdhar Samhita has mentioned the five types of Pratishyaya and more description is added in the commentary.
- Bhaishajya Ratnawali and Chakradutta have mentioned the treatment of Pratishyaya only.
- In Harita Samhita, description of the nasarogas is given as per the doshas, and common principles of their treatment are mentioned.
- Gadanigraha, Madhavnidana and Yogaratnakara have given the same description on the basis of Sushruta and Charaka. In some places some new opinions are also given, but the descriptions are almost the same.
- From all the above references it means that Pratishyaya is a disease which should be studied from all the texts. It also proves its importance among all the nasarogas.

VISHESHA CHIKITSA

- In Charaka Samhita, specific treatment is given of the different types of Pratishyaya, except for Sannipatik Pratishyaya. As he mentioned that Sannipatik Pratishyaya is incurable, he has not mentioned any treatment for it.

- Sushruta Samhita has explained specific treatment for different types of Pratishyaya along with Kriminashaka Chikitsa.
- Ashtanga Sangraha and Ashtanga Hridaya has also explained specific treatment for the different types of Pratishyaya. There is a detailed explanation of the treatment of Dushta Pratishyaya in Ashtanga Sangraha, which is not given in detail in the other Ayurvedic classics.
- In Kashyapa Samhita a general line of treatment of Pratishyaya is explained and no specific treatment for the different types of Pratishyaya is mentioned. Treatment of Jeerna Pratishyaya is also given.
- In Bhaishajya Ratnawali, specific treatment for the different types of Pratishyaya is given along with the Amavastha, Pakwavastha and Jeernavastha. General treatment and kriminashak treatment is also explained. Treatment for Dushta Pratishyaya is not mentioned.
- Chakradatta has mentioned the same treatment for Pratishyaya as explained in Bhaishajya Ratnawali.
- In Gadanigraha, specific treatment for the different types of Pratishyaya is given along with the Amavastha and Pakwavastha. General treatment for Pratishyaya is also explained. Treatment for Sannipataja Pratishyaya, Dushta Pratishyaya and kriminashak chikitsa is not mentioned.
- In Bhavaprakasha, a general line of treatment for Pratishyaya is mentioned. Specific treatment for the different types of Pratishyaya and Krimihara chikitsa is not mentioned.
- In Bhava Prakasha, specific treatment for the different types of Pratishyaya is given along with the Amavastha and Pakwavastha. General treatment for Pratishyaya is also explained. Treatment for Sannipataja Pratishyaya and Dushta Pratishyaya is not mentioned.

CONCLUSION

Eloquent the Nidana simplifies the evaluation of the Dosha vitiation, the determination of the Vyadhi's Sadhya Asadhyata, the analysis of the Samprapti, and the appropriate treatment strategy. The best therapy methods used to control the ailment would not be helpful if the Nidanans are not addressed and avoided; for this reason, our Acharyas have explicitly said that "Sanksepataha Kriyayoge Nidana Parivarjanam." Nidana can act alone, in concert, or in combination to activate Doshagati, aggravate an existing illness, or cause Dosha Prakopa to cause new disease.

REFERENCES

1. Kaviraja Atrideva Gupta, Astanga Hridaya of Vagbhata, "Vidyotini" Hindi Commentary, edited by Vaidya Yadunandana Upadhyaya, Uttar Tantra Reprint edition Chapter 19 Versus 2, Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhawan, 2009; 701.
2. Chakrapanidatta, Chakradatta, Vaidhyaprabha hindi commentary by Indradeva Tripathi, edited by Ramanatha Dwivedi, Chaukhamba Sanskrita Bhavana, Varanasi, reprint; 2010; Netraroga Chikitsa/3; page no 347.
3. Acharya Sushruta, Sushruta Samhita with commentary by Dalhanacharya and on Nidanasthana by Gayadasacharya, edited by Vd. Yadavji Trikamji Acharya & Narayana Ram Acharya, Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashana, Varanasi, 2008; Uttarantra 24/19; page no. 652.
4. Acharya Vagbhata, Ashtanga Sangraha with shashilekha commentary by Indu, edited by Shivaprasada Sharma, Chaukhamba Sanskrit series office, Varanasi, 1st edition, 2006; Uttarantra 24/2-3, page no 744.
5. Acharya Vagbhata, Ashtanaga Hridaya with Sarvanga Sundari commentary by Arunadutta and Ayurveda Rasayan commentary by Hemadri, edited by Pandit Sadashivashastry Paradkara, Chaukhamba Surabharati prakashana, Varanasi, Reprint; 2007, Uttarantra 20/2, Page no 843.
6. Yogaratnakara with Vidyotini hindi commentary by Vd Laksmipati Shastri, edited by Bhishagratna Bramhashankara Shastri, Chaukhamba Prakashana, Varanasi, edition reprinted, 2007; Nasaroga Chikitsa/2, page no. 327.
7. Yogaratnakara with Vidyotini hindi commentary by Vd Laksmipati Shastri, edited by Bhishagratna Bramhashankara Shastri, Chaukhamba Prakashana, Varanasi, edition reprinted, 2007; Nasaroga nidana/2, page no. 327.
8. Yogaratnakara with Vidyotini hindi commentary by Vd Laksmipati Shastri, edited by Bhishagratna Bramhashankara Shastri, Chaukhamba Prakashana, Varanasi, edition reprinted, 2007; Nasaroga nidana/2, page no. 327.
9. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, revised by Charaka and Dridhbala with Ayurveda Dipika commentary by Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Yadavji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukhamba Surabharati prakashana, Varanasi, 2008; Chikitsasthana 26/136; page no. 606.
10. Shri Govind Das, Bhaishajya Ratnawali, 'Vidyotini' hindi commentary analysis with appendixes by Shri Kaviraj Ambikadutta Shastri, 18th revised edition and enlarged by

Bhishagratna Shri Bramhashankar Mishra, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi; 2007; 63/16; page 986.

11. Chakrapanidatta, Chakradatta, Vaidhyaprabha⁴ hindi commentary by indradeva Tripathi, edited by Ramanatha Dwivedi, Chaukhamba Sanskrita Bhavana, Varanasi, reprint, 2010; Netraroga Chikitsa/16: page no 345.
12. Mohan Bansal Diseases of Ear Nose And Throat 3rd edition chapter 41: 345-347.
13. P.L. Dhingra Assisted by Deeksha Dhingra Diseases of Ear, Nose and Throat 8th Edition Chapter, 30: 194.